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Deployment of Big Data for Tertiary Education Management in Nigeria

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Abstract: This paper examined the importance of deploying big data for the management of tertiary education in Nigeria. The paper is a position paper that employed the use of secondary data. The secondary data were collected from print and online publications. Content analysis was used to select and limit the literature to the minimum size. The paper concluded that big data can be deployed in different aspects of tertiary education management in Nigeria. The paper emphasized that big data can aid effective data management in tertiary institutions (academic calendar planning, academic planning, examinations planning, school admission, and financial planning), and support effective implementation of teaching, research, and provision of community services in the various institutions across the country. Based on this, the paper recommends an increment in the funding of tertiary institutions to enable tertiary institutions to procure information communication technologies that will support the operation and deployment of big data in the management of the various institutions in Nigeria. Secondly, tertiary institutions management should organize training for staff to be able to use the big data facilities in the institutions.

Keywords: Big data, Tertiary Education, Management.

Introduction

Tertiary education is a structured, organized system designed to foster the holistic development of individuals while driving societal transformation through comprehensive teaching, research, and community service, as well as reflecting the diversity of society through the range of people, cultures, lifestyles, and values it encompasses (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie, 2023; Ogunode & Odo, 2023; Ogunode & Ayeni, 2023). This form of education, which includes both undergraduate and graduate credentials such as certificates, diplomas, and academic degrees, is non-compulsory and pursued after high school in institutions like colleges, polytechnics, and universities (Top-hat, 2023). It can be

delivered through various modalities, including traditional in-person instruction, virtual platforms, or distance learning, ensuring accessibility to a broad range of learners while adapting to the needs of an evolving global society (Top-hat, 2023). In this context, tertiary institutions serve not only as centers of advanced learning but also as microcosms of society, reflecting the values, cultures, and complexities of the broader world in which they operate (Ogunode & Odo, 2023; Ogunode & Ayeni, 2024).

The term "tertiary" refers to the third rank or order, and in the context of Nigeria, tertiary education denotes the third level of education, commonly referred to as higher education (Okai & Botimi-Slaboh, 2019). Tertiary education in Nigeria is synonymous with higher education and is responsible for producing the human capital required for societal and national development (Okai et al., 2019). As the highest tier of education, tertiary education plays a pivotal role in driving national development and transformation by equipping individuals with the necessary skills, knowledge, and information essential for productivity, wealth creation, prosperity, good health, competitiveness, and scientific and technological advancement (Ofojebe & Chukwuma, 2015). It serves as a key vehicle for societal progress and individual empowerment, ensuring the nation's ability to adapt to global challenges and opportunities.

Tertiary education in Nigeria aims to provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in both formal and informal settings to meet the diverse needs and interests of all citizens. Its goals include offering high-quality career counseling and lifelong learning programs that equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary for self-reliance and workforce success. Additionally, it addresses skill shortages by producing skilled manpower aligned with labor market demands, while promoting scholarship, entrepreneurship, community service, and fostering national unity and international understanding (FRN, 2013). The realization of these goals is contingent upon effective planning and the availability of up-to-date data.

One of the major problems threatening the development of tertiary education is the problem of poor data management. The problem has affected the effective planning of tertiary education resulting in uncontrolled student admission, shortage of facilities, and personnel, and poor curriculum planning. The population of students and poor organization due to poor data management are among the factors that have contributed to the poor quality of the institutions. The problem of data management seems to be a problem common to all institutions. Big data was developed to address the problem of managing large data in institutions. Cloud (2024) noted that big data refers to extremely large and diverse collections of structured, unstructured, and semi-structured data that continue to grow exponentially over time. These datasets are so huge and complex in volume, velocity, and variety, that traditional data management systems cannot store, process, and analyze them. The amount and availability of data is growing rapidly, spurred on by digital technology advancements, such as connectivity, mobility, the Internet of Things (IoT), and artificial intelligence (AI) (Cloud, 2024; Olatunde-Aiyedun & Hamma, 2023). As data continues to expand and proliferate in various institutions especially tertiary institutions, new big data tools emerged to help institutions and companies collect, process, and analyze data at the speed needed to gain the most value from it. Big data describes large and diverse datasets that are huge in volume and also rapidly grow in size over time. Big data is used in machine learning, predictive modeling, and other advanced analytics to solve business problems and make informed decisions (Cloud 2024). It is important to examine the benefits of deploying big data for the management of tertiary education in Nigeria.

The research method employed for this study is the documentary research method, where secondary sources of data like journals, books, and other online materials were sought through the Google Scholar search engine. A documentary research method is a non-positivist method of inquiry. Non-positivism is

a method of carrying out research that tries to explain social phenomena with the aid of a research question, without necessarily testing hypotheses (Ayeni, Saman, & Sani, 2019).

Concept of Big Data

The concept of Big Data in education is part of the ongoing fourth “educational” revolution, which demands a shift from traditional educational models focused on the transfer of knowledge from teacher to student, towards more dynamic and data-driven approaches. Big Data in education involves the in-depth analytics of the educational system by measuring, collecting, analyzing, and presenting vast amounts of both structured and unstructured data related to students and the educational environment. By harnessing historical data, Big Data systems allow for more precise and informed decision-making. The challenge of processing these vast data sets is addressed through advanced communication technologies, which make data management and analysis more accessible and actionable. Thus, Big Data represents a transformative tool for rethinking concepts like effective learning, subject mastery, and the overall structure of education systems.

Big Data is often described in terms of the “3 Vs” — volume, velocity, and variety — although additional characteristics such as veracity, variability, and value are increasingly emphasized (Cloud, 2024). Volume refers to the sheer scale of data generated from numerous sources and devices, often continuously. Velocity captures the rapid speed at which data is produced, requiring real-time or near real-time processing for meaningful analysis. Variety highlights the heterogeneity of data, which can be structured, unstructured, or semi-structured, ranging from spreadsheets and databases to text, images, and sensor data.

In addition to these primary attributes, veracity addresses the quality and accuracy of Big Data, acknowledging that large datasets can be error-prone or incomplete. Variability points to the ever-changing nature of data, including shifts in meaning and data collection methods. Finally, value underscores the importance of extracting useful insights from Big Data, ensuring it holds relevance and can inform decision-making (Cloud, 2024). Together, these characteristics frame the complexity and potential of Big Data in various fields, including education, business, and technology. The central idea behind Big Data is that greater visibility into any area leads to better insights, allowing for more informed decisions, growth opportunities, and enhanced business models. To make Big Data work effectively, three key actions are required:

- i. **Integration:** Big Data collects vast amounts of raw information, often measured in terabytes or petabytes, from various sources. This data must be received, processed, and transformed into a format usable by business analysts for effective analysis.
- ii. **Management:** Big Data requires significant storage capacity, whether on-premises, in the cloud, or through hybrid solutions. Data needs to be stored in the appropriate format and processed for real-time availability. Increasingly, businesses rely on cloud solutions for their scalability and extensive computational resources.
- iii. **Analysis:** Analyzing Big Data is crucial to deriving actionable insights; without this, the investment in Big Data offers little return. Effective analysis includes using tools for data visualization, such as charts, graphs, and dashboards, to present insights in a clear and comprehensible way to stakeholders (Cloud, 2024).

Big Data analysis involves both quantitative and qualitative approaches. According to Cloud (2024), five specific types of data are often used for these objectives:

1. Personal information,

2. Data on student interactions with digital learning systems (e-books, online courses),
3. Reports on the effectiveness of learning materials,
4. Administrative or system-wide data,
5. Forecast input data.

Analyzing various models and approaches reveals three key areas of focus:

1. Thinking (emphasizing critical and creative thinking),
2. Interaction (focusing on communication and collaboration),
3. Self-regulation and self-organization (including reflexivity) (Danielkivych, 2022).

These areas highlight the broad applicability of Big Data in improving decision-making and driving educational and organizational transformation.

Application of big data for tertiary education Management in Nigeria

Big data can be applied in different aspects of tertiary institutions. Big data can aid effective data management in tertiary institutions, and support effective implementation of teaching, research, and provision of community services.

Data management

Big Data can play a crucial role in the effective management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria by addressing data management challenges and enabling efficient data collection, computation, and analysis for informed planning and decision-making. According to Danielkivych (2022), Big Data offers academic institutions the ability to integrate critical platforms and applications that manage various aspects of their operations, enhancing overall efficiency and significantly reducing costs. The adoption of advanced technology is transforming how institutions analyze information and make decisions regarding academic performance, faculty effectiveness, technological integration, and organizational interactions.

In areas such as school planning, academic scheduling, and exam timetable preparation, Big Data can be utilized to develop realistic, implementable plans that improve efficiency. As tools for data collection and analytics improve, Big Data enables administrators to access detailed information, making it easier to predict trends and make informed decisions about student admissions. This data-driven approach helps target growth strategies and optimize resource allocation at the level of specific training programs rather than applying general solutions across the institution (Danielkivych, 2022; Olatunde-Aiyedun et al., 2024). In their work on the "Role of Digital Technologies in Enhancing Environmental Geography Education," Olatunde-Aiyedun, Daniels, and Olamoyegun (2024) highlight how digital technologies, particularly Big Data, can play an integral role in improving the planning and management of educational activities. By incorporating digital platforms into environmental geography education, institutions can enhance learning experiences and streamline administrative processes. Big Data analytics, for example, can help tailor academic schedules and curriculum designs based on student performance trends and feedback, ensuring that resources are aligned with educational demands and that programmes remain relevant and efficient.

Moreover, Big Data can aid environmental geography educators in assessing the effectiveness of digital tools used in the classroom, such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and remote sensing technologies, by tracking how students interact with these tools and measuring learning outcomes. This allows for more precise adjustments in instructional techniques and technology integration, ultimately

improving both student engagement and academic success. By leveraging Big Data insights, institutions can make more targeted decisions, ensuring that digital technologies are not only enhancing academic delivery but also contributing to the institution's broader mission of fostering growth and development. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, the integration of Big Data and digital technologies will be pivotal in managing various aspects of tertiary education, from academic scheduling to admissions processes, while supporting innovative educational practices like those in environmental geography. The ability to analyze and act on vast amounts of data will enable institutions to stay agile and responsive to the needs of students and society at large (Olatunde-Aiyedun et al., 2024).

In the areas of students' admission into institutions, Big Data can help in the systematic arrangement, selection process, and timely organization of student data in administrative offices. Danielkivych (2022) asserted that with the help of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, administrative staff in student management can track the online activity of potential students across social networks and mobile devices. When a potential new student visits the college's website, "cookies" can be used to retarget ads to them on other platforms. This process can increase student enrollment and, consequently, boost institutional profits. In the areas of institutions' personnel data management and students' data management, Big Data can be effectively used to streamline the organization and retrieval of critical data, enhancing both academic and administrative processes. Ekpo and Aiyedun (2020) discuss how the integration of innovative teaching strategies, such as the Photographic Album Teaching Strategy, can improve students' performance in environmental education.

Similarly, in data management, Big Data analytics can track academic progress, monitor student engagement, and assess the effectiveness of various instructional strategies. By employing data-driven tools, institutions can not only manage vast amounts of personnel and student data more efficiently but also make more informed decisions about academic interventions and resource allocation, leading to improved overall performance and educational outcomes. Big Data facility is an infrastructure. Therefore, Infrastructural development enhances human security (Ayeni, Andeshi, & Uzoigwe, 2022). It is safe to say that Big Data enhances human security.

Teaching programme implementation

Danielkivych, (2022) concluded that lecturers or teachers can use the information received to create a more productive learning environment and the most effective assessment of the results and quality of the lessons. Analytics can provide real-world insights into quiz errors, incorrect student responses, and time spent on completing assignments. This allows teachers to adjust their instructions as needed and ensure optimal student outcomes in the short term.

Research programme implementation

Big data can support the effective implementation of research programmes in various tertiary institutions. Research according to Bako (2005) is a systematic search and investigation for increasing the sum of knowledge; and research and development (R&D) is the search and application of this knowledge for the development of improved products, services, and industrial processes of capital development. Research is seen by Ajoku (2004) as the search for knowledge, truth, similarities, and relationships, and finding solutions to problems through the systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. Ogunode and Abubakar (2020), Ogunode, Ayeni, and Ogwuche (2024) submitted that research is the second cardinal programme of higher institutions. Research is very important to the development of the society. Research is conducted mostly in the higher institutions environment with the objective of solving problems affecting society. The academic staff is saddled with the responsibilities of carrying out research in the universities.

Research in tertiary institutions has been conducted by lecturers, students, and researchers. Data are collected by most students and academic research. Big data can help in the effective management of research data in institutions. Danielkievych, (2022) observed that academic staff in tertiary institutions can use big data in research on student achievements and identify potential opportunities for more in-depth participation in processes. For example, they can analyze dropout rates, total enrollment, and student achievement rates to optimize the curriculum.

Provision of community service programme

Community service can be more implemented by the deployment of big data facilities to reach many communities. Community service programmes of tertiary institutions are social and economic projects that are designed to serve the community purposely in the fields such as health, social service, environmental protection, education, urban and rural redevelopment, welfare, recreation, public facilities, public safety, and child care. Community service programmes are organized projects, and supervised activities that are a direct benefit to the community and are designed to improve the welfare of the whole community (Lawinside, 2024). A community service programme is an organized and planned service programme of higher institutions for the benefit and betterment of their host community. Community service programmes of higher institutions are community-inclined services initiated by the institutions to develop the communities. Community services of higher institutions are services provided by institutions to benefit the community people (Ogunode, Iyabode & Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2022).

Big data can be applied in the areas of management of large data of communities in respect of health community data, gender data, and youth empowerment programme data. Big data support community data collection and management. Big data aids effective community programme planning. Big data support effective monitoring of internal processes, supply chain processes, and the performance of all processes in the community. Communities are increasingly turning to big data to discover new ways to improve decision-making, opportunities, and overall improved service delivery. For example, big data can be harnessed to address the challenges that arise when information is dispersed across several different systems that are not interconnected by a central system. By aggregating data across systems, big data can help improve decision-making capability. It also can augment data warehouse solutions by serving as a buffer to process new data for inclusion in the data warehouse or to remove infrequently accessed or aged data. Big data can lead to improvements in overall operations by giving organizations greater visibility into operational issues. Operational insights might depend on machine data, which can include anything from computers to sensors or meters to GPS devices (Villanovau University 2020). Big data provides unprecedented insight into the community' decision-making processes by allowing community-based institutions and governments to track and analyze service provision, impact, recommendations, and other social economic policies that are known to influence community development.

The benefits of Big Data in tertiary education according to Danielkievych, A. (2022) include;

1. It helps to identify areas where students may succeed or require additional support. Individually defined patterns make it simpler to understand particular needs and develop optimal personalized education strategies. This also helps students save time when choosing the right faculty.
2. Track student activities, such as how long they take, what sources they use to prepare, what topics are ignored, and more. Big data can also be used to track students' careers after graduation. It will also render them an invaluable service in choosing the right college and course of study.

3. It helps to create unique programs for each student. Even if there are hundreds of students in a college or university, different programmes can be created for each of them using the so-called *blended learning* approach (simultaneous online and offline learning).
4. Get predictions about future performance. It will also help to quickly analyze the course syllabus before it is introduced into the curriculum.
5. Assess dropout rates. By identifying the top reasons why students leave the university, professors can develop programmes and strategies to better retain students.
6. Predict candidates more accurately, as well as analyze the factors influencing the application for training. Such knowledge will enable institutions to adjust resource allocation and recruitment strategies. This data flow will also help potential students analyze information about universities and colleges not only in their home country but around the world.
7. Better understand the strengths and weaknesses of your students. A teacher gets the opportunity to analyze the heap of information as a whole and draw unambiguous conclusions. They recognize the problem and take action to prevent more complex issues. After a thorough analysis, the programme is easier to adjust and get more personalized. Hence, it enhances student performance and achievement.
8. Reduce dropout rates associated with a lack of understanding of the complexity of the student's chosen specifications. The analysis of information helps to assess the real abilities and talents of students and determine the best academic specification for them.
9. Adjust current learning strategies. Educators may realize that a particular plan is not working well for a particular group of students. Timely adjustments can help them move forward and keep up.
10. Increase performance. Thanks to the collection of information, educators constantly monitor trends. After a deep analysis, they can clearly understand the strengths and weaknesses of each student.

Challenges of implementing big data analytics

While big data has many advantages, it does present some challenges that organizations must be ready to tackle when collecting, managing, and taking action on such an enormous amount of data. The most commonly reported big data challenges include according to Cloud (2024):

- **Lack of data talent and skills.** Data scientists, data analysts, and data engineers are in short supply—and are some of the most highly sought-after (and highly paid) professionals in the IT industry. Lack of big data skills and experience with advanced data tools is one of the primary barriers to realizing value from big data environments.
- **Speed of data growth.** Big data, by nature, is always rapidly changing and increasing. Without a solid infrastructure in place that can handle your processing, storage, network, and security needs, it can become extremely difficult to manage. This is why it has been argued that infrastructure can empower people (Ayeni, 2017).
- **Problems with data quality.** Data quality directly impacts the quality of decision-making, data analytics, and planning strategies. Raw data is messy and can be difficult to curate. Having big data does not guarantee results unless the data is accurate, relevant, and properly organized for analysis. This can slow down reporting, but if not addressed, you can end up with misleading results and worthless insights.

- **Compliance violations.** Big data contains a lot of sensitive data and information, making it a tricky task to continuously ensure data processing and storage meet data privacy and regulatory requirements, such as data localization and data residency laws.
- **Integration complexity.** Most companies work with data siloed across various systems and applications across the organization. Integrating disparate data sources and making data accessible for business users is complex, but vital if you hope to realize any value from your big data. For the inevitable role of Big Data infrastructure, scholars have noted that massive infrastructural development like Big Data is suitable support for the development of entrepreneurship skills and industrialisation (Ayeni, Abdullahi, & Andeshi, 2021).
- **Security concerns.** Big data contains valuable business and customer information, making big data stores high-value targets for attackers. Since these datasets are varied and complex, it can be harder to implement comprehensive strategies and policies to protect them. The inability to provide for Big Data facility is a threat to human security. Thus, it has been argued that the inability of political authorities to provide people with basic infrastructure is a threat to human security (Ayeni, Sani, & Haruna, 2023, p.136). The need for security concern is germane because it is “a state of not being financially, emotionally, psychological and materially threatened” (Ayeni & Beji, 2018, p. 17)

Findings

The paper disclosed that big data can be deployed in different aspects of tertiary education management in Nigeria. The paper emphasized that big data can aid effective data management in tertiary institutions (academic calendar planning, academic planning, exams planning, school admission, and financial planning), support effective implementation of teaching, research, and provision of community services in the various institutions across the country.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper discussed the importance of deploying big data for the management of tertiary education in Nigeria. The paper concluded that big data can be deployed in different aspects of tertiary education management in Nigeria. The paper emphasized that big data can aid effective data management in tertiary institutions (academic calendar planning, academic planning, exams planning, school admission, and financial planning), support effective implementation of teaching, research, and provision of community services in the various institutions across the country.

Based on the findings of this study, the paper recommends an increment in the funding of tertiary institutions to enable tertiary institutions to procure information communication technologies that will support the operation and deployment of big data in the management of the various institutions in Nigeria. Tertiary institutions management should organize training for staff to be able to use the big data facilities in the institutions.

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